

1 **ID factor mobilization during lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
9 nuclear factors encoded by the ID family as lineage commitment factors of embryonic stem cells of the
10 human embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. Jiang, H., Du, M., Li, Y., Zhou, T., Lei, J., Liang, H., Zhong, Z., Al-Lamki, R.S., Jiang, M. and Yang,
13 J., 2022. ID proteins promote the survival and primed-to-naive transition of human embryonic stem cells
14 through TCF3-mediated transcription. Cell Death & Disease, 13(6), p.549.